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Fairness in funding research by lottery

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Abstract: In this paper, we contribute to the ongoing discussion on the allocation of research funding by granting bodies: traditional peer review or lotteries. We focus here on two prominent definitions of fairness: whether funding decisions are meritocratic and whether they are unbiased. We synthesize the existing literature to propose a taxonomy of available funding lottery types. Then we run a simulation experiment to estimate how traditional peer review and the various lottery types compare in terms of fairness. Results show that, counterintuitively, under the conditions examined here traditional peer review is not necessarily more meritocratic than most lottery types and most lottery types are not necessarily less biased than traditional peer review.

Introduction

Recently, some research funding organizations have introduced an element of randomness in their funding procedures where some of the proposals recommended by the review panel for funding are funded directly, and some are put in a lottery pool and grant winners are chosen by lot (Adam, 2019; Avin, 2019; Conix et al., 2021; Ioannidis, 2011). Opinions on lotteries are divided. Traditional peer review is considered more desirable – or *fairer* – by some scholars (e.g. Bedessem, 2020; Reinhart & Schendzielorz, 2020; Smaldino et al., 2019). Others consider lotteries to be fairer (Adam, 2019; Conix et al., 2021; Gildenhuis, 2020; Horbach et al., 2022).

This disagreement has two roots: (1) alternative notions of fairness; (2) alternative ways of implementing a funding lottery. Crucially, traditional peer review and the various implementations of a funding lottery might better align with different notions of fairness.

This paper identifies the range of possible implementations of a funding lottery and explores their relationship to some dimensions of fairness in science funding. We use Monte Carlo simulations to compare funding decisions by traditional peer review panels and lottery implementations. The simulation allows us to explore the various funding systems vis-a-vis competing notions of fairness (we select two for this paper).

Fairness in funding

The concept of *fairness* features prominently in debates on which approach – traditional peer review or funding lotteries - is best for funding science. What exactly is meant by fairness, however, varies. For instance, some scholars focus on some of the flaws of traditional peer review – such as the concentration of resources in the hands of few – and ponder whether funding lotteries could be fairer in these regards (Adam, 2019; Gildenhuis, 2020; Gillies, 2014; Osterloh & Frey, 2020). Some discuss costs: whether lotteries are fairer in the sense that they can speed up the selection process and reduce workload for applicants and reviewers (Avin, 2015; Conix et al., 2021; Fang & Casadevall, 2016; Gross & Bergstrom, 2019). Some have further considered the fairness of the potential psychological and career effects of funding lotteries (Reinhart, 2021; Reinhart & Schendzielorz, 2020). Finally, some have discussed the fairness of lotteries in the eyes of applicants themselves (see e.g. Barlösius & Philipps, 2022; Liu et al., 2020; Philipps, 2021; Reinhart & Schendzielorz, 2020), of funders and of the wider public (Barnett, 2016; Bouacida & Foucard, 2020).

In these lively debates, two themes recur: *meritocracy* and *bias*. Meritocracy refers to the idea that a funding decision is fair if it rewards merit; that is, that some applicants deserve funding by virtue of their harder or better work (echoing the “desert-based principles” - see Lamont & Favor, 2017). Traditional peer review is a (arguably imperfect) tool to assess merit; whereas a funding lottery is blind to merit. Thus, intuitively, traditional peer review is considered better suited to reward merit than funding lotteries.

Scholars argue, however, that traditional peer review is not at all impartial, and that reviews can be influenced by demographic or other characteristics of the funding proposals, applicants or reviewers that should not matter at all (Lee et al., 2013). Intuitively, funding lotteries should be blind to these characteristics, and thus be more conducive to fairer (i.e. unbiased) funding decisions.

Taxonomy of funding lotteries

The discussion of which funding system is merit-fairer and which is bias-fairer is complicated by the fact that there exist various types of funding lotteries with potentially different strengths and weaknesses. While Phillips (2021) offers a coarse classification of lottery procedures our need to distinguish among characteristics relevant for fairness dictates that we expand the taxonomy. Building on Phillips (2021) we classify funding lotteries by the prominence of random allocation in the selection process, from Type 0 (no lottery) to Type 4 (full lottery) (see Table 1).

Type 0 denotes a traditional peer review panel, where no funding decision is based on chance. At the opposite end of the spectrum we have Type 4 – full lottery (allocation is guided solely by the lottery; no peer review panel is involved). In a Type 4 lottery all formally eligible proposals enter the lottery pool and winners are selected at random (uniform). Although to our knowledge no research funding institution has ever adopted a Type 4 funding system, we include Type 4 in our study because it is discussed in the literature (Greenberg, 1998; Roumbanis, 2019) and can serve as a limit case.

Table 1. Funding systems from traditional peer review (Type 0) to mixed lotteries (Types 1-3) and full lottery (Type 4).

Type	Description	Is a lottery	Is a mixed lottery	Has focal randomization	Adopted in some funding schemes by
0	Traditional peer review				Most funders
1	Tie-breaking mixed lottery	✓	✓	✓	Swiss National Science Foundation
2	Mixed lottery with bypass	✓	✓	✓	Volkswagen Foundation; Austrian Science Fund
3	Mixed lottery of fundable proposals	✓	✓		Health Research Council of New Zealand; Science for Technological Innovation (New Zealand)
4	Full lottery	✓			N/A

Types 1-3 are mixed lotteries. They sit between a traditional peer review system (Type 0) and a full lottery (Type 4) with elements of both a peer review panel and a lottery. Closer to traditional peer review are mixed lotteries with so-called focal randomization (Brezis, 2007): these are lottery Types 1 and 2. With focal randomization the review panel divides the submitted proposals into three sets. The first set comprises the most promising proposals to be directly recommended for funding. The second is the focal randomization set (or just “lottery pool”).

The lottery pool comprises all funding-worthy proposals that are somewhat “less good” than the first set. The third set are proposals that are not recommended for funding. In sum, focal randomization is a device that allows review panels to recommend some proposals directly for funding, and some other proposals to be eligible for entering a funding lottery. There are different ways of implementing focal randomization, and therefore we further distinguish between lottery Type 1 and Type 2.

In Type 1 lotteries, focal randomization takes the shape of a *tie-breaking mixed lottery*.¹ Randomness plays a very secondary role in tie-breaking mixed lotteries. Mostly, randomness here is a way of making an arbitrary decision among equally meritorious proposals.

In Type 2 lotteries, focal randomization is achieved with a bypass option. While in Type 1 lotteries the review panel has the *option* of creating a lottery pool to resolve ties, in Type 2 the panel *has to* set up the lottery pool. The panel can also recommend some proposals for direct

¹ For example: If ten proposals can be funded in a particular competition, the review panel will recommend funding the top ten. A tie-breaking mechanism will be needed if there are ties for tenth place. In Type 1, all proposals that tie for tenth best constitute the focal randomization set, and the tie is resolved with a lottery (i.e. by sampling with uniform probability). In Type 0, we assume that the panel, unable to break the tie, will recommend all tying proposals for funding. In Type 1, the tie is always broken at random. As a consequence, Type 0 can lead to the recommendation of more proposals than other Types.

funding: these proposals *bypass* the lottery.² For example, if funding is available for ten proposals, the review panel will put in the lottery pool the best proposals (specifically, a number of them greater than ten). In a mixed lottery with bypass, the panel has furthermore the option of recommending exceptionally promising proposals for funding thus bypassing the lottery.

Mixed lotteries with bypass are thought of as a way to promote transformative, innovative or just riskier research projects (thanks to the lottery), while ensuring that excellent proposals are not being missed to bad luck (thanks to the bypass).

Last, Type 3 lotteries are mixed lotteries without focal randomization: they are *mixed lotteries of all fundable proposals*. The role of peer review is comparatively limited in Type 3 lotteries, since panels are only tasked with identifying all eligible proposals that meet some baseline quality criteria.

Simulation experiment

Assume there exists a review panel that ranks all proposals from best to worst with perfect accuracy: this is our *reference panel*, and its evaluation is our *reference evaluation*. Compared to the reference panel, the evaluation of an “everyday” peer review panel is (1) coarser, meaning that sometimes two or more proposals are both indistinguishably good; (2) prone to errors, i.e. the evaluation is less accurate due to lack of competence, time or other resources; (3) biased – that is, the evaluation is affected by some attributes that should not matter, like e.g. the gender of the applicant.

This is the logic of our simulation experiment. To measure how meritocratic a selection procedure is we calculate the rank correlation (Spearman's ρ) between the reference evaluation and the funding recommendations by the everyday panel (aided or replaced by a lottery, as the case may be). The higher the correlation, the better the procedure is able to allocate funds based on merit. Similarly, to measure how biased a selection procedure is, we correlate the attribute that should not matter (e.g. gender) with the funding recommendation – the higher the correlation, the stronger the effect of bias on the final decision.

We simulate the evaluation by a reference panel and the various selection procedures (Types 0-4) using Monte Carlo simulations. Each run of the simulation model simulates a funding call where some formally eligible research proposals compete for funding. Proposals have two uncorrelated attributes: their reference evaluation and a “bias” factor. We randomly draw the reference evaluation from a left-skewed bell-shaped distribution in the range $[0,1]$ – this reflects the assumptions that that a higher reference evaluation is indicative of a good proposal, and that most proposals tend to be good.³ The distribution of the bias factor is harder to imagine – we therefore draw it from a uniform distribution in $[0,1]$.

Then, proposal evaluations by an everyday panel are generated by drawing from a normal distribution with mean=0 and s.d.=1. In order to model error and bias in the panel evaluation we further assume that the evaluations by the everyday panel correlate with both the reference evaluation ($r=0.5$ – so, less than perfect correlation) and with the bias factor ($r=0.2$ or 0.5 – a higher value models a very biased everyday panel). Lastly, in order to model a coarse evaluation by the everyday panel, we discretize their evaluation. To do so we also need to determine how

² Practically, funders allow the bypass option by giving reviewers so-called “wildcards” or allowing the direct funding of proposals upon unanimous approval by the review panel.

³ Technically, we use a beta distribution with parameters $\alpha=10$; $\beta=3$. A similar implementation and discussion on the empirical underpinnings of these assumptions is found in previous work (Feliciani et al., 2022).

many grades are available for the panel to choose from. There are $G \times N - (N - 1)$ available grades, where N is the number of reviewers and G is the granularity of the evaluation scale in use by each reviewer. In other words, fewer reviewers or Likert-scales with fewer available grades result in a coarser evaluation by the everyday panel.

Here follows a summary of the model parameters and the values we explored. Underlined values show the parameter configurations we used to produce the plots in the simulation results.

- *Target funding rate* = $\{0.25, \underline{0.5}, 0.75\}$. Indicates minimum proportion of submissions to be recommended for funding.
- *Sufficient merit* = $\{0.25, \underline{0.5}, 0.75\}$. On a scale from 0 (bottom) to 1 (top), “sufficient merit” indicates which minimum grade by the everyday panel qualifies a fundable quality proposal. Higher sufficient merit implies stricter quality requirements.
- *Lottery choice rate* (for Type 2 lotteries) = $\{0.25, \underline{0.5}, 0.75\}$. Proportion of proposals that a Type 2 panel will choose by lottery. The remainder will be directly chosen.
- *Panel bias* = $\{\underline{0.2}, 0.5\}$. Correlation between the evaluation by the everyday panel and the bias factor – i.e. the proposal attribute, like e.g. gender, that should in fact not correlate with the evaluation.
- *Granularity of the evaluation scale*, $G = \{3, \underline{5}, 10\}$. Number of grades available to reviewers.
- *Size of the review panel*, $N = \{3, \underline{5}, 7\}$. Number of reviewers in the everyday panel.

For each parameter configuration we run 100 independent simulations. For each simulation, we assume there are 100 eligible proposals to be chosen from. And for each simulation, we simulate all types of selections (0 through 4) 100 times each, in the end taking their average merit and bias.

Results and discussion

Figure 1 shows the simulation results. Surprisingly for us, mixed lotteries (Types 1-3) lead to funding allocations that are basically as meritorious and as biased as the decision of a traditional panel (Type 0). Only Type 4 lotteries sacrifice merit for less biased decisions. These results generally hold across all the parameter configurations we explored.

Figure 1. Predicted merit and bias in traditional peer review (Type 0) vs various forms of funding lottery (Types 1-4).

Moreover, our assumption that no ties are broken in a Type 0 system means more proposals can be recommended for funding under Type 0 than under Types 1-4. Under some conditions, this puts Type 0 at a disadvantage, leading to the counterintuitive result that Types 1-3 decisions can sometimes correlate *more* with merit than Type 0 decisions.

These results suggest that any form of involvement of a peer review panel – even just to determine the lottery pool – can lead to decisions that reflect merit and simultaneously inject bias into the funding process. Thus, under some conditions, merit and bias – the main arguments in favor of or against (mixed) lotteries – might not be a robust guiding principle to choose one or another funding system.

Clearly, more theoretical and empirical research is still needed. Relevant differences between the various lottery types and traditional peer review might emerge, for example, if fairness is defined and operationalized differently, or if other variants are introduced to the taxonomy (e.g. redistributive corrections). Since different redistributive corrections can apply to different types of funding procedures, and their effects can vary, redistributive corrections are a promising next step to further this line of inquiry.

References

- Adam, D. (2019). Science funders gamble on grant lotteries. *Nature*, 575(7784), 574–575. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-019-03572-7>
- Avin, S. (2015). Funding Science by Lottery. In U. Mäki, I. Votsis, S. Ruphy, & G. Schurz (Eds.), *Recent Developments in the Philosophy of Science: EPSA13 Helsinki* (Vol. 1, pp. 111–126). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-23015-3_9
- Avin, S. (2019). Mavericks and lotteries. *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part A*, 76, 13–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shpsa.2018.11.006>
- Barlösius, E., & Philipps, A. (2022). Random grant allocation from the researchers' perspective: Introducing the distinction into legitimate and illegitimate problems in Bourdieu's field theory. *Social Science Information*, 053901842210766. <https://doi.org/10.1177/05390184221076627>
- Barnett, A. G. (2016). Funding by Lottery: Political Problems and Research Opportunities. *MBio*, 7(4), e01369-16, /mbio/7/4/e01369-16.atom. <https://doi.org/10.1128/mBio.01369-16>
- Bedessem, B. (2020). Should we fund research randomly? An epistemological criticism of the lottery model as an alternative to peer review for the funding of science. *Research Evaluation*, 29(2), 150–157. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvz034>
- Bouacida, & Foucard, R. (2020). *The acceptability of lotteries in allocation problems: a choice-based approach* (Lancaster University, Department of Economics, Lancaster).
- Brezis, E. S. (2007). Focal randomisation: An optimal mechanism for the evaluation of R&D projects. *Science and Public Policy*, 34(10), 691–698. <https://doi.org/10.3152/030234207X265394>

- Conix, S., De Block, A., & Vaesen, K. (2021). Grant writing and grant peer review as questionable research practices. *F1000Research*, *10*, 1126. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.73893.1>
- Fang, F. C., & Casadevall, A. (2016). Research Funding: The Case for a Modified Lottery. *MBio*, *7*(2), e00422-16, /mbio/7/2/e00422-16.atom. <https://doi.org/10.1128/mBio.00422-16>
- Feliciani, T., Morreau, M., Luo, J., Lucas, P., & Shankar, K. (2022). Designing grant-review panels for better funding decisions: Lessons from an empirically calibrated simulation model. *Research Policy*, *51*(4), 104467. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2021.104467>
- Gildenhuis, P. (2020). Lotteries make science fairer. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, *7*(sup2), S30–S43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2020.1812485>
- Gillies, D. (2014). Selecting applications for funding: Why random choice is better than peer review. *RT. A Journal on Research Policy and Evaluation*, Vol 2, No 1 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.13130/2282-5398/3834>
- Greenberg, D. S. (1998). Chance and grants. *The Lancet*, *351*(9103), 686. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(05\)78485-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(05)78485-3)
- Gross, K., & Bergstrom, C. T. (2019). Contest models highlight inherent inefficiencies of scientific funding competitions. *PLOS Biology*, *17*(1), e3000065. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000065>
- Horbach, S. P. J. M., Tjldink, J. K., & Bouter, L. M. (2022). Partial lottery can make grant allocation more fair, more efficient, and more diverse. *Science and Public Policy*, scac009. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scac009>
- Ioannidis, J. P. A. (2011). Fund people not projects. *Nature*, *477*(7366), 529–531. <https://doi.org/10.1038/477529a>
- Lamont, J., & Favor, C. (2017). Distributive Justice. In *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Winter 2017). Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2017/entries/justice-distributive/>
- Lee, C. J., Sugimoto, C. R., Zhang, G., & Cronin, B. (2013). Bias in peer review. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, *64*(1), 2–17. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.22784>
- Liu, M., Choy, V., Clarke, P., Barnett, A., Blakely, T., & Pomeroy, L. (2020). The acceptability of using a lottery to allocate research funding: A survey of applicants. *Research Integrity and Peer Review*, *5*(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-019-0089-z>
- Osterloh, M., & Frey, B. S. (2020). How to avoid borrowed plumes in academia. *Research Policy*, *49*(1), 103831. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2019.103831>
- Philipps, A. (2021). Research funding randomly allocated? A survey of scientists' views on peer review and lottery. *Science and Public Policy*, scab084. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scab084>

Reinhart, M. (2021). *Open Science as an Engine of Anxiety: How Scientists Promote and Defend the Visibility of Their Digital Selves, while Becoming Fatalistic about Academic Careers* [Preprint]. SocArXiv. <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/2vr7j>

Reinhart, M., & Schendzielorz, C. (2020). The lottery in Babylon—On the role of chance in scientific success. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 7(sup2), S25–S29. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2020.1806429>

Roumbanis, L. (2019). Peer Review or Lottery? A Critical Analysis of Two Different Forms of Decision-making Mechanisms for Allocation of Research Grants. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 44(6), 994–1019. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0162243918822744>

Smaldino, P. E., Turner, M. A., & Contreras Kallens, P. A. (2019). Open science and modified funding lotteries can impede the natural selection of bad science. *Royal Society Open Science*, 6(7), 190194. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.190194>